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PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF DRUGS IN PREGNANT WOMEN ATTENDING ANTENATAL OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT OF A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Drug treatment during pregnancy presents a special concern. Pharmacoepidemiological studies can measure the extent of prescription and teratogenic drug use in pregnant women. Objective: To understand the prescribing trends & pharmacological class wise drug consumption; to classify the drugs prescribed during antenatal care according to the US-FDA category; to determine the number of drugs prescribed as per National List of Essential Medicine [NLEM]; to analyze the prescription based on WHO core drug prescribing indicators; to find the prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy. A prospective observational study was conducted at SSIMS & RC, Davangere, Karnataka for a period of six months. Methodology: The data about 200 pregnant women were collected from OBG OPD and documented. The appropriateness of the prescribing pattern was analyzed as per US FDA risk category, WHO prescribing indicators and as per NLEM. Results: Drugs prescribed in generic name was 35%, most prescribed route of administration was oral. All pregnant women were having at least primary education. Most prescription was encountered in 2nd trimester with average number of drugs prescribed with 3.5. The most associated medical condition was anemia in which mild anemia was high in 2nd trimester followed by Nausea & Vomiting. Most commonly prescribed drug was calcium supplement followed by Iron. Category C drugs were prescribed more. No X category drugs were prescribed. Conclusion: Our study revealed a careful prescribing behavior by the physicians to the pregnant women under antenatal care visiting outpatient department of a tertiary care teaching hospital.

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INTRODUCTION

Antenatal care is organized medical service including examination and advising a pregnant woman with the objective that every wanted pregnancy culminates in the delivery of a healthy baby without impairing the health of the mother.^[1]

Drug use during pregnancy is complicated by the changing biochemical dynamics of the mother and the fetus. Drugs given during pregnancy can affect the fetus by producing a lethal, toxic or teratogenic effect on the embryo or fetus; by constricting placental vessels, through impairing gas and nutrition exchange between fetus and mother, by producing severe uterine hypertonia resulting in anoxic injury, or indirectly, by changing the biochemical dynamics of the mother.

As there are numerous gaps in knowledge about deleterious consequences for the fetus, prescription drug use by pregnant women should be viewed as a public health issue.^[2, 3]

Teratogenesis is the induction of development abnormality in a fetus by a drug taken during the early stages of pregnancy; the period from 2 to 8 weeks of gestation is the most critical. Some conditions such as Epilepsy are difficult to manage during pregnancy because of the risk of teratogenesis.

The principles of prescribing in pregnancy includes ;

- ◆ Should avoid drugs unless the benefit to the mother greatly outweighs the risk to the fetus.
- ◆ Only use drugs when there is previous experience.
- ◆ Use the lowest dose for the shortest time possible.
- ◆ Choose the least harmful drugs if a range of alternatives is available.

Thalidomide crisis in the 1960's and the teratogenic effects of use of Diethylstilbestrol In 1971 led the US Food and Drug Administration [US FDA] to demonstrate safety and efficacy of any drug before it is marketed. The most well-known classification was introduced by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 1979, using the letters A, B, C, D and X for five categories.

Category A	Adequate clinical studies have shown no risk to fetus in any trimester.
Category B	Animal studies have not shown adverse effects on the fetus and there are inadequate clinical studies.
Category C	Animal studies have shown adverse effects, no adequate clinical studies. May be useful in pregnancy despite potential risks.
Category D	There is evidence of risk to human fetus, but potential benefits may be acceptable despite potential risks. (e.g. in a life - threatening situation)
Category X	Animal/human studies show fetal abnormalities. Risks involved clearly outweigh benefits. Contraindicated in women who are or may be pregnant. ^[4]

It provides therapeutic guidance for the clinician. Category A is considered the safest category but some drugs from categories B, C and D are also used during pregnancy. Category X is the only rating that denotes a drug is absolutely contraindicated for use during pregnancy.^[39]

WHO INDICATORS

Appropriate use of drugs is one essential element in achieving quality of health and medical care for patients and the community as a whole. The World Health Organization (WHO) concluded that a rational use of drugs requires that patients receive medications appropriate to their clinical needs, in doses that meet their own individual requirements for an adequate period of time, and the lowest cost to them and their community.

NLEM

Essential medicines are those that satisfy the priority healthcare needs of majority of the population. The primary purpose of NLEM is to promote rational use of medicines considering the three important aspects i.e. cost, safety and efficacy. Furthermore it promotes prescription by generic names.

OBJECTIVES

To understand the prescribing trends & pharmacological class wise drug consumption; to classify the drugs prescribed during antenatal care according to the US-FDA category; to determine the number of drugs

prescribed as per National List of Essential Medicine [NLEM]; to analyze the prescription based on WHO core drug prescribing indicators; to find the prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy. A prospective observational study was conducted at SSIMS & RC, Davangere, Karnataka for a period of six months.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A prospective observational study was conducted to analyze the drug prescribing pattern in pregnant women in OBG OPD of a tertiary care teaching hospital, Davangere for a period of six months. 200 pregnant women were enrolled in the study pregnant women unwilling to participate and patients diagnosed with acute or chronic condition requiring hospitalization were excluded.

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College Davangere. The study was carried out by regular visit to Outpatient Department of OBG for collecting the case sheets of pregnant women. The detailed information on the prescription records given at the time of enrollment was documented in a separately designed data collection form. An informed consent was taken from each & every subject or subject's representative before the commencement of data collection. The participants were informed about the objective of the study and complete information regarding the research work. Socio-economic and educational status were obtained by interviewing subject or their representatives. Data about Hb was collected from patient medication chart. The obtained data was analyzed to find out the prescribing pattern of drugs in the OBG Outpatient Department of the hospital. The drugs were classified according to the pharmacological class and their teratogenic potential. The prescriptions were analyzed for the most commonly associated medical condition and the trimester in which the most drugs were prescribed. Then the appropriateness of the prescribing pattern was analyzed as per US FDA risk category, WHO core drug prescribing indicators and NLEM.

RESULTS

Out of 200 pregnant women, 98 (49%) were from the age group of 18-24 years, 93 (46.5%) from 25-30 years and only 9 (4.5%) from the age group >30 years. 103 (51.5%) obtained primary education, 57 (28.5%) obtained secondary education, 31 (15.5%) were graduated and 9 (4.5%) were post graduated. 83 pregnant women visited the OPD in their second trimester followed by 67 and 50 pregnant women in their third and first trimester respectively. Out of 200 prescriptions, the average number of drugs per prescription was found to be 3.3 in first trimester, 3.5 in second trimester and 3.0 in third trimester. In 200 prescriptions, 724 drugs were prescribed. The most commonly associated condition was Anemia 105 (52.5%) followed by Nausea & Vomiting 33 (16.5%), history of previous abortion 17 (8.5%) and Hypothyroidism 13 (6.5%).

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF ANEMIA ACCORDING TO WHO CLASSIFICATION.

ANEMIA (n=105)		
	Hb range	n (%)
Mild Anemia	9-10.9 g/dl	79 (75.2%)
Moderate Anemia	7-8.9 g/dl	25 (23.8%)
Severe Anemia	<7 g/dl	1 (0.0095)

Out of 105 pregnant women with Anemia, 79 (75.2%) were mildly anemic, 25 (23.8%) were moderately anemic and only one patient was severely anemic.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF DRUGS BASED ON PHARMACOLOGICAL CLASS.

Sl no.	Pharmacological class (n=56)	Frequency (n=724)	Percentage (%)
1	Vitamins and Minerals (7)	260	35.912
2	Protein supplement (1)	79	10.912
3	NSAIDs (4)	63	8.702
4	Antacids (2)	50	6.906
5	Anti-microbials (12)	38	5.25
6	Anti-histamines (3)	36	4.972
7	Proton pump inhibitors (1)	29	4.001
8	Progestin derivatives (1)	25	3.453
9	Anti-hypertensives (5)	23	3.177
10	Vaccines & Sera (2)	22	3.038
11	H2 receptor blockers (1)	20	2.762
12	Digestives (1)	17	2.35
13	Corticosteroids (2)	15	2.072
14	Thyroid hormone (1)	15	2.071
15	Uterine relaxants (2)	8	1.104
16	Anti-diabetic agents (2)	7	0.967
17	Anti-epileptic agents (2)	4	0.552
18	Anti-cholinergics (1)	3	0.414
19	Stool softner (1)	3	0.414
20	Anti-emetics (1)	2	0.28
21	Probiotics (1)	2	0.276
22	Electrolytes (2)	2	0.276
23	Urinary alkalinizer (1)	1	0.139

56 different drugs from 22 pharmacological classes were prescribed. From 56 drugs, a total of 724 drugs were prescribed. More commonly prescribed class of drug was Vitamins and Minerals 260 (35.912%) followed by 79 (10.912%) Protein supplement, 63 (8.702%) NSAIDs, 50 (6.906%) Antacids and 38 (5.25%) Anti-microbials.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF US FDA RISK CATEGORIZATION.

Category	No. of drugs (n=56)	Percentage (%)
Category A	5	8.93
Category B	17	30.36
Category C	24	42.85
Category D	3	5.36
Category X	0	0
NA	7	12.5

Out of 56 drugs, Category C 24 (42.85%) were prescribed more followed by Category B 17 (30.36%) and Category A 5 (8.93%). No Category X drugs were prescribed. Information about 7 (12.5%) drugs were not available.

TABLE 4: WHO PRESCRIBING INDICATORS.

SL NO.	PRESCRIBING INDICATORS ASSESSED	TOTAL	AVERAGE/ PERCENTAGE	WHO STANDARD DERIVED
1	Avg. number of drugs per prescription	724	3.62	1.6 – 1.8
2	Percentage of prescription with antibiotics	38	19%	20.0 – 26.8
3	Percentage of prescription with injections	48	24%	13.4 – 24.1
4	Percentage of drugs prescribed in generic name	253	34.94%	100
5	Percentage of drugs from NLEM	328	45.303%	100

Commonly prescribed route of administration was found to be oral that is 637 (88%), followed by IV 68 (9.4%), vaginal 8 (1.1%), topical 7 (1%) and subcutaneous 4 (0.5%). Among 724 drugs 253 (35%) drugs were prescribed in generic name and 471 (65%) drugs were prescribed in brand name. 32 (57.14%) drugs were prescribed from NLEM and 24 (42.86%) were not from NLEM.

DISCUSSION

Drug use during pregnancy requires a special concern and care. The present study about the prescribing pattern of drugs in pregnant women conducted over a period of six months on 200 pregnant women attended OPD OBG revealed the antenatal care practice in the rural tertiary hospital scenario. Out of 200 prescriptions we got a total of 724 drugs, in which only 253 drugs (35%) were prescribed in generic name and 42.86% drugs were from NLEM. Oral preparations were the more prescribed choice of route of administration. It made aware that in most of the prescription supplementary drugs were given which includes Iron, Folic acid, Vitamins, Minerals, Calcium and Protein supplements. In our study mainly Calcium supplements were given which became polemic with other analogous studies by Sharma et al, Ghia et al and S. R Gowde et al in which Iron/Folic acid/ multivitamin or their combination were given primarily.^[5, 4, 1]

It was an encouraging result that no women were illiterate, this result was coincided with the study conducted by S. R. Gowde et al where there pregnant women profile shown to be literate conducted in an urban area.^[1] This finding will help the women to understand about the need of the therapy and care to be taken during the pregnancy period. It is evident from our study that more number of prescriptions was encountered in second trimester, 83 prescriptions with an average number of drugs of 3.3. In third trimester an average of 3.9 drugs were prescribed in a total prescription of 67 which was noticeable that maximum number of drug prescribed was 3.3±1.1 in second trimester in a study conducted by Ghia et al in Maharashtra.^[4]

In our study 52.5% (105) of the surveyed women were having Anemia. Anemia is the term used to describe the condition in which there is a reduction in the concentration of haemoglobin in the blood stream to a level below 11gm/dl for pregnant women. 40% of all maternal peri-natal deaths are linked to anaemia.^[6] It was found in the study of S. R. Gowde et al that one third women were anemic; Percentage of women having mild anemia in 1st, 2nd, 3rd, trimester in their study were found to be 81%, 83% and 82% respectively, percentages of women having moderate anemia in 1st, 2nd and 3rd trimester were found to be 16%, 12% and 16% respectively, percentages of women having severe anemia in 1st and 2nd trimester were only 2%. Women about 0.005% had severe anemia in their third trimester.^[1] While in our study mild Anemia was found to be 32.38% and 12.38% in 1st & 2nd trimester respectively. Moderate Anemia was 20% and 7.62% in 1st and 2nd trimester respectively. Only one woman came with severe Anemia in third trimester. Anemia depends upon the nutritional condition of the women which in turn relay upon the socio-economic determinants of the population. Most of the women were belonging to Class B.

The distribution of associated medical conditions was differed from other studies. A similar study by Kumarjit et al in Tumakuru, Karnataka, among diseases suffered Pre-eclampsia was the most frequent (45.33%) followed by gastrointestinal disturbances (32%).^[7] The drug use was mainly for URTI, fever with chills, vaginal discharge and Nausea & Vomiting in the study by S. R. Gowde after Anemia.^[1] But in our study it was found that drug use was for anemia followed by Nausea & Vomiting, history of previous abortion, Hypothyroidism, UTI and Hypertension. Eleven different anti-microbials were prescribed in this study and the most prescribed one was Cefixime. Other agents include combination of Tinidazole, Clotrimazole & Clindamycin followed by Amoxicillin and Azithromycin. Labetolol was the most prescribed anti-hypertensive followed by Amlodipine & Methyldopa. Pantoprazole was prescribed over Ranitidine in anti-secretory drugs. Doxylamine succinate was prescribed more for Nausea & Vomiting.

Here in our study we have used US-FDA risk categorization system for evaluating the teratogenic risk associated with the prescribed drug use in pregnancy by using the data available in Micromedex & Lexicomp. Category C drugs were prescribed more followed by Category B, A & D. It was a comforting data that no X Category drugs were given. Our study came into contravention with the study by S. R. Gowde et al and Ghia et al in which most prescribed Category was A followed by B, C & D.^[1,4]

The results from all the similar studies were different in terms of prescribing patterns of the drugs by the physicians.

CONCLUSION

There was a considerable variation in prescribing levels between practices and overall drug use pattern is rational with few exceptions. Drug therapy was given for a pre-existing problem or a problem that aroused as result of pregnancy. The prescribing pattern was not adhered to WHO criteria for rational use of drug. Very less number of drugs were prescribed in generic name and drugs from essential list of medicine were also very low.

FDA established strict regulations regarding drug labeling, the use of medications in pregnancy, requiring demonstrations of safety and efficacy of any drug before it becomes commercially available. It was satisfactory in our study result that no X Category drug was given.

Anemia was prevalent among pregnant women in first two trimester which have serious adverse consequences in both mother and baby, management of anemia in pregnancy was accorded a very high priority.

Our study helps in exploration of ideas related to the general consideration in prescribing.

Our study revealed a careful prescribing behavior by the physicians to the pregnant women under antenatal care visiting outpatient department of a tertiary care teaching hospital.

We concluded that further efforts directed to develop data on the safety of drugs during pregnancy are needed. The current study implies that drug use in pregnant women should be monitored. Health-care providers and women must be made aware of the medications on the real or potential risks to the fetus.

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